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**ANALYSIS OF SUGIRA MURYANGO PROJECT IN COMMUNITY BEHAVIOR CHANGES:
CASE OF MALE ENGAGEMENT IN HOUSEHOLD RESPONSIBILITY IN NGOMA
DISTRICT IN RWANDA (2020-2022).**

BY

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ABSTRACT:

Unity of household members is a cornerstone of family development and gender equality is one of the key steps to accelerating sustainable development. Overall objective of this study was to analyze the contribution of Sugira Muryango Project in community behavior change, a case of male engagement in household responsibility, in Ngoma district, Rwanda. The study sought to answer three questions: (i) what are the contributions of Sugira Muryango Project to changing male's behavior towards household responsibility? (ii) Are there current challenges facing male to involve in household responsibility? and (iii) What are the best practices introduced by Sugira Muryango in changing Males' behavior towards household responsibilities? Total population were 325, calculated sample size to 180 and purposive, stratified and random sampling were three sampling methods used. Findings showed that 34.4% of respondents testified that that creation of male champion groups approach contributed in changing males' behavior towards household responsibilities. 90% of respondents appreciated approach of home visitation and 87.8% of respondents recognized creation of male saving and credit association approach as a good contributor of improving household development and changing living conditions of families. Findings also showed that, home visitation, males champions and creation of saving and credit association has high positive correlation with changing males behavior towards participating in household work (unpaid care work). Therefore, based on the interpretation of collected and analyzed data during this study which aimed to assess the contribution of Sugira Muryango to male engagement in household responsibilities in Eastern province, Ngoma district. The researcher concluded that, Sugira Muryango project has hugely contributed to male engagement in household responsibilities through three programs: creation males' champions, household home visitation and saving groups and credit creation association and researcher recommended to disseminate these approaches to bigger population beyond scope of Sugira Muryango.

Keywords: *Sugira Muryango Project, Community Behavior and Change Male Engagement in Household Responsibility*

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1. Introduction

Unity of household members is one of the cornerstones of a family development.

Human interactions either socially or economically are influenced by behavior. These interactions are the basis of development; and, if development is about change, then innovative solutions leading to change should be about people willing to change their behaviors. Behavior changes have been an issue due to people are not always in control of the problem that determines their behavior. People's behavior is affected by external factors such as interpersonal relations, physical environment, economic determinants, and policy framework (CBS, 2019).

Community projects not only contribute to socio-economic development but more importantly influence people's behavior changes. Community projects around the world have been playing an important role in the development of society to enhance the quality of life and improve community behavior (Mughal, 2017). Although behavioral models of community intervention are growing in popularity, applying behavior modification techniques in public places presents a variety of logistical and moral challenges.

Africa has been facing the problem of colonialization that did not affect the behavior of African ancients but also affect the current population toward social life. African indigenous tribes have been severely impacted by colonialism, which has left an inescapable mark on politics, economics, culture, and social conventions (Shawn O. Utsey, 2014).

In East Africa Community, Population Service Kenya is a Non-Government Organization with the mission of acknowledging that behavior change has moved to the center stage in the work of African governments and their domestic

2. Statement of the problem

Despite global outstanding steps toward gender equality, males still behave as economic providers whereas mothers are responsible for household responsibilities (Barnett, 2014). The World Health Organization's 2018 report, "Nurturing Care Framework," revealed that

and international partners to foster better health outcomes in communities (Rebecca, 2022).

The Government of Rwanda has discovered that gender equality is one of key steps to accelerating sustainable development; the recent Gender Gap Report 2020 of the World Economic Forum ranked Rwanda as the first country in Africa and the 09th country globally in promoting gender parity between men and women (MIGEPROF, 2020). The government of Rwanda is increasingly emphasizing human capital development to support the socio-economic transformation of the country.

Ngoma district has launched Farmers Laud Greening GIRINKA Project, a project that aims to transform the behavior of the community about modern agriculture and enhance the contribution of livestock to a household development (RAB, 2022) through harmonious collaboration of household member.

In the context of fulfilling the gap between men and females in household work, Strong Families, herein "Sugira Muryango" Project started to implement its interventions in Rwanda with the mission of enhancing Males' engagement in household activities.

Despite great effort engaged in promoting gender balance, male engagement in household responsibilities is still a problematic concern in the community. Although male play a vital role in family and community development, they are still playing a low proportional in household responsibilities or in unpaid care works. In recent years, different organizations have initiated to change community towards male engagement in household responsibilities

Therefore, this study analyzed the contribution of Sugira Muryango Project in community behavior changes, case of Male Engagement in Household Responsibility in Ngoma District in Rwanda.

historically, women have been the primary caregivers. This strategic document, however, acknowledges the need to mobilize men to take on a central parenting role, as men's involvement in childrearing, while growing, is still relatively limited globally.

In her study, she found that men acknowledged the importance of physical presence, support, and love for their children and contribute in household responsibility. However, due to poverty, men spent most of their time outside of their home seeking jobs or doing income-generating activities, which results in ignoring housework responsibility (Mandisa Malinga, 2021). Apart from this, Chebbi in 2022 found that women carry out at least two and half times more unpaid household and care work than men.

Despite the promising evidence that men's potential to contribute in positive ways as males and contribute to daily household responsibility but research of Alexann found that, men still are

3. Objectives of the study

This study was to analyze the contribution of Sugira Muryango Project in the main objective of community behavior change, a case of male engagement in household responsibility, in Ngoma district, Rwanda. Specifically, the study sought to:

- [1] Analyze contribution of Sugira

4. Research Questions

Research questions is an approach that enable the researcher to specify the issues or problem he/she wants to focus on. They break down the project into more manageable tasks that would need to be investigated and completed. The following are the questions formulated for further investigation:

5. Concept of Variables

This is about the definition of the main terms of our research topic namely human resource management practices, financial resource management practices, the time resource management practices and public Participation practices according to different authors. Its main

Sugira Muryango Project. Sugira Muryango is a Rwandan father-engaged early child development and violence prevention home visiting program that uses active coaching to build parent capabilities and increase responsible parenting of both mothers and fathers to promote

facing with the problem of gender norms and expectations, social factors (Clara Alemann, 2021). In Rwanda 89 percent of women perform household activities; moreover, women in Rwanda spend on average 23.5 hours per week on domestic activities, while men spend only 5 hours per week (Olivier, 2017).

Based on the above present research undertaken in this field, a gap in analyzing contribution of project or programs in changing behavior changes specifically targeting Male engagement in household responsibility. Hence the researcher, want to close this information gap lies on the evidences in Ngoma district.

Muryango Project to changing male's behavior towards household responsibility

- [2] Assess current challenges facing males to involve in household responsibility
- [3] Examine best practices introduced by Sugira Muryango Project in changing males' behavior towards household responsibility.

Q.1.What are the contributions of Sugira Muryango Project to changing male's behavior towards household responsibility?

Q.2.Are there current challenges facing male to involve in household responsibility?

Q.3.What are the best practices introduced by Sugira Muryango in changing Males' behavior towards household responsibilities?

purpose is to help the reader to easily have the general understanding of used concepts, (OECD, 2012).

early childhood development (ECD) and prevent violence. Sugira Muryango has targeted families in extreme poverty with young children aged 0 – 36 months. The project operates in three districts of Rwanda “Ngoma, Rubavu, and Nyanza of Rwanda (Betancourt, 2021).

Community Behavior Change. This refers to the larger, macro-level environment which can either promote or deter behaviors, it is influenced by the situational context in which the individual lives and in which social relationships are nested.

Male Engagement in Household Responsibility. This refers to the practice of enabling men and boys to engage positively around household works with their female

6. Theoretical Review

Theory of gender equality

The concepts of gender equality and gender equity are based on the assumption that the distribution of opportunities, resources, and responsibilities between women and men should not disfavor either group. Gender equality concerns equal rights (absence of gendered discrimination) whereas gender equity concern's needs-based approaches (Hammarström et al., 2014). Women's integrity and autonomy in relation to men have clearly improved in Western society as a result of the ongoing development of instruments for the defense and advancement of

Theory of Change

Groups and project stakeholders determine the conditions they think must occur for their long-term goals to be achieved through the rigorous yet inclusive Theory of Change approach. These circumstances are represented graphically in a causal framework as outcomes. The Theory of Change approach, or simply Theory of Change, is another name for the process of developing a Theory of Change.

Therefore, you could be referring to the method or the end result when you hear or say "Theory of Change.". The Theory of Change needs participants to be clear on long-term goals, define measurable indicators of success, and develop strategies to attain goals, just like any good planning and evaluation process for social change. It differs from all previous techniques for describing initiatives in the following ways: By

Community Behavior Change Projects are established to facilitate dialogue, participation and, engagement of entire community to change positive social norms and behaviors (Ruziev, 2022)

partners, this includes performing unpaid household work, providing parental care to the kids and, doing household work intentionally (Cabiness, 2019).

gender equality in the face of the corresponding indifference of social and political structures based on gender stereotypes. For instance, it can appear that traditional gender roles are shifting in Western society if men are no longer expected to support their families financially and women are no longer expected to pursue careers.

In this way, they share a classic sexist conviction in real concerns but an egalitarian belief in concepts or ideas. Thus, we know that ethical principles are a symbolic referent occupying a space in decision making, but not always moving it (Castillo-Mayén & Montes-Berges, 2014).

outlining the requirements for achieving objectives, it illustrates a causal pathway from one point to another. You must state underlying assumptions that can be verified and assessed. It shifts your perspective on efforts so that you start with what you want to accomplish rather than what you are currently doing.

The assumptions that stakeholders use to describe the change process reflected in the change framework are stated in the theories of change that we construct. All proposed causal relationships between expectations and short-, medium-, and long-term outcomes are predicated on assumptions. In the present, Sugira Muryango has used approaches including males' champions group, home visitation and saving and credit association to change behavior of men towards household responsibility.

7. Empirical review

Due to misconceptions about gender equality and gender norms, issues pertaining to the male role in the family continue to be obstacles. A vital and urgent revolution to put care at the center of societies and the lives of the global population includes men's full participation in care activities. Whether at home, in childcare or elder care, or in larger social structures and economies, care is essential to nations and economies around the world. However, domestic labour has historically been underfunded, unpaid, or both (Promundo, 2021). Whether at home, in childcare or elder care, or in larger social structures and economies, care is essential to nations and economies around the world. However, domestic labour has historically been underfunded, unpaid, or both (Promundo, 2021).

Between 2014 and 2016, the percentage of eligible men who used some form of parental leave versus women increased from 54 percent to 98 percent (Batthyany, 2019). Another study found increases in men's involvement in care work on weekdays (in Sweden and Canada) and especially on weekends (in those two countries, as well as Germany) (Neilson, 2014). Males' engagement and investment (both tangible and non-tangible) in household are seen as the pathway through which Males influence mainly child development. There is a tendency to characterize South African Males as being largely absent from the lives of their children, with a minority of children living in the same household as both their biological parents (Parliamentary Liaison Office, 2019).

In Latin America, kids both boys and girls see women as being responsible for their care which is clearly of the strongest sources of rigid and inequitable social norms related to caregiving. Therefore, breaking this cycle and engaging men in caregiving is a key to promoting generational changes in the gender balance of caregiving. Sons and daughters who see and experience men involved in their caregiving, whether at home or

8. Conceptual framework

From the discussion provided above, the conceptual framework showed the logical relationship between independent variable which is Methods, approaches of Male engagement are

in a day care centers or school are more likely to believe that caregiving is also a man 'responsibility (Barker, 2008). In his research, Barker found that, there are relatively few men in Latin. America region who are in professions in which they can provide care for younger children and pay attention to household responsibility such as day centers, cooking or primary schools.

In Chile, men may see their domestic work as a kind of gift to women, or as something to do on special occasions (if a spouse is ill or tired), but seldom as a question of justice or equality. Some men, research has found may take on significant portions of domestic labor, including childcare, when they are out of work, and may even report this to be positive. Some men, research has found, may take on significant portions of domestic labor, including childcare, when they are out of work, and may even report this to be positive (Olavarría, 2000).

Africa has been facing with the problem of gender norms and discrimination of gender towards work, men have been ignoring unpaid household work which has been duties of women. The study conducted in Tanzania showed that men's engagement in household activities was significantly associated with living in an urban setting, being younger, having at least some formal schooling (Chahalís, 2021).

Rwanda's public health system has also integrated an evidence-based parent-training program P model in partnership with a local nongovernmental organization (NGO). MenCare's Program (for papa/Male) parent training intervention has been used in more than 15 countries in the past 10 years. It has been rigorously evaluated in several of these countries, including Rwanda, where it is on track to be implemented on a national scale by the Ministry of Health (Kazimbaya, S., Nzabonimpa, A., Pulerwitz, J., Sayinzoga, 2018).

measured by eradicating gender norms, contribution to positive parenting and improvement of household living conditions and dependent variable is outcome of Male

engagement in household responsibility. The independent Variable is expected to relate the dependent variable through gender norms, culture of the nation, huge responsibility of males to feed a family, misunderstanding of males towards gender balance, resisting to change, unclear

Figure 1. Conceptual framework.

interventions, misunderstanding of gender balance, family conflict and poverty and historical background. The researcher developed a conceptual model which guided this research shown in the figure 1.

9. Materials and Methods

This study applied qualitative and quantitative research (descriptive), and correlation research designs. The target population was 180 respondents. Stratified sampling and random sampling techniques were then used to select the respondents. The instruments of data collection were questionnaires technique. Methods of

analyzing data of this research include descriptive statistical method which was used to describe the frequency, percentages, and mean and standard deviation of data collected. The correlation coefficient matrix analysis was applied to test the relationship between variables.

10. Findings and Discussions of the Results

Data were collected through questionnaires addressed to 180 respondents, and a document review especially the progress of reports on this project in previous years ago. Data obtained were analyzed quantitatively using computer software of SPSS IBM version 23.0. The participation rate was 100.0% in responding to the questions, and this helped to continue research with editing, coding, recording, classifying, and tabulating data towards the analysis. Results were interpreted and presented in accordance with the study objectives. Findings indicated that the majority of respondents were females, this was justified by 52.8% of respondents being females, while 47.2% of respondents were females. In

addition to this majority of households were headed by males (95.0%)

The findings showed that more men changed their behaviors in participating in the Sugira Muryango project activities and approaching women as women respondents more than men. In this study, researchers have analyzed the contribution of male engagement in changing their behavior toward household responsibility conserving to what extent Males Champions Groups, Home Visitation and, Saving and Credit Association all created as interventions that should lead to men's transformation toward household responsibilities.

Profile of Respondents

Here, the study presents the findings on the profile of respondents including but not limited to gender; Age group of the respondents;

educational characteristics, and head of households as detailed in the following tables.

Table 1. Gender distribution of the respondents

Gender distribution of the respondents	Frequency	Percent
Female	85	47.2
Male	95	52.8
Total	180	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2022

In the table above Gender distribution of the respondents shows that the majority of respondents were males, this was justified by

52.8% of respondent's males, while 47.2 % of respondents were female. This is true because the study targeted to males than females.

Table 2. Age distribution of the respondent

Age distribution of the respondents	Frequency	Percent
Between 21 and 30 years old	25	13.9
Between 31 and 40 years old	75	41.7
Between 41 and 50 years old	44	24.4
51 and above years old	36	20.0
Total	180	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2022

Concerning the age of respondents, 13.9% of respondents have age between 21 and 30 years; 41.7% of respondents have age between 31 and 40 years, 24.4% of respondents have aged between 41 and 50 years; while those who have

aged 51 years and above were 20.0% respondents. This implies that the study was inclusive and engaged participants from the different age groups in order to capture different views

Table 3. Educational characteristics of the respondents

Education level	Frequency	Percent
No education	72	40.0
Primary education	60	33.3
Secondary education	20	11.1
Vocational training	16	8.9
University	12	6.7
Total	180	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2022

Concerning education level, 40% of the respondents are non-educated. 33.3% of the respondents have primary education. 11.1% of respondents have secondary education, 8.9% of respondents have vocational training, and 6.7% of respondents have university degrees. However,

during focus group discussions, respondents have said that there is little relationship between males' education with their engagement in household responsibilities. But they have suggested that the government of Rwanda and development partners to invest in education for elderly people in the country.

Table 4. Head of household

Head of household	Frequency	Percent
Male	171	95.0
Female	9	5.0
Total	180	100.0

Source: Primary data ,2022

Concerning the head of household, the statistics show that 95.0% of the respondents were, males while 5.5% were females. This implies that there is still a gap to fulfill in terms of determining who

should be the head of the family but at the same time relating to the culture of the nation and the social life of the citizens

Descriptive analysis

Mean, standard deviation, and standard error were computed using descriptive analysis, and then, Correlation matrix, Regression analysis It is broken down into measures of central tendency and measures of variability (spread). Measures of central tendency include the mean,

(Model summary), Analysis of Variance (ANOVA Table), and Regression coefficient.

median, and mode, while measures of variability include standard deviation, variance, minimum and maximum variables

Correlation matrix

A correlation matrix is simply a table that displays the correlation coefficients for different variables. The matrix depicts the correlation between all the possible pairs of values in a table. It is a powerful tool to summarize a large dataset and identify and visualize patterns in the given

data. The correlation matrix shows the correlation values, which measure the degree of the linear relationship between each pair of variables. The correlation values can fall between -1 and +1. If the two variables tend to increase and decrease together, the correlation value is positive

Table 6. Correlation matrix

Statement		Outcomes of the project	Creation of male champions	Household home visitation	Creation of male saving and credit association
Outcomes of the project	Pearson Correlation	1	.375**	.417**	.472**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	180	180	180	180
Creation of male champions	Pearson Correlation	.375**	1	.242**	.270**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.001	.000
	N	180	180	180	180
Household home visitation	Pearson Correlation	.417**	.242**	1	.893**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001		.000
	N	180	180	180	180
Creation of male saving and credit association	Pearson Correlation	.472**	.270**	.893**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	180	180	180	180

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The findings showed that male champions, household home visitation and saving groups, and credit creation associations have a high positive

relationship with males engaging in household. This implies that Sugira Muryango needs to put many efforts to reinforce these approaches.

Meaning that; male champions groups, home visitation, and, the creation of saving and credit association has relationship with changing males’

behavior towards engaging in household responsibilities (doing unpaid care work).

Regression analysis (Model summary)

Regression is a statistical method used in finance, investing, and other disciplines that attempt to determine the strength and character

of the relationship between one dependent variable (usually denoted by Y) and a series of other variables (known as independent variables).

Table 6. Regression analysis (Model summary)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.537 ^a	.289	.277	.34804

a. Predictors: (Constant), Creation of male saving and credit association, Creation of male champions, Household home visitation

The model showed that male champions, household home visitation and saving group and credit creation association contributes up to 27.7% of male engaging in household

responsibilities. Moreover, because the standard error is less than 2 means that the mean is more accurate in reflection of the actual population and the results are considered reliable.

Conclusion

Based on the interpretation of collected and analyzed data during this study which aimed to assess the contribution of Sugira Muryango to male engagement in household responsibilities in Eastern province, Ngoma district evidence. The researcher concluded that Sugira Muryango project has hugely contributed to

male engagement in household responsibilities through three programs: the creation of male champions, household home visitation and saving groups and credit creation association. This implies that community have to scale up the programs to bigger beneficiaries beyond Sugira Muryango’s boundaries.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the study recommends that:

- i. Empower saving and credit associations by offering result-based management and loan management
- ii. Sugira Muryango is recommended to look at the issue of financial assistance that could follow theoretical interventions due to some of the households don’t participate intentionally and this will improve their morale, and social and economic development in their families
- iii. Disseminate approaches used by SM to more households as they have indicated contributing to changing males ‘behavior towards engaging in household responsibilities hence improving the living condition of household
- iv. Home visitation should be restructured and visit families in their free hours or possibly during the weekend due to will increase the intention of discussants mainly household members and their full availability
- v. Government of Rwanda should revisit the article on gender balance and revamp it in order to remove conspiracy (males understand as it has ridiculed them while females tend to overlap males
- vi. Start curriculum from lower schooling to high schooling about the importance of male participation in household responsibility as a

way of eradicating the issue of misunderstanding the concept.

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